

MONOCHROMATIC SOLUTIONS OF EXPONENTIAL EQUATIONS

Tom Brown

Department of Mathematics, Simon Fraser University, Burnaby, B. C., Canada
 tbrown@sfu.ca

Received: 1/13/14, Revised: 10/6/14, Accepted: 1/26/15, Published: 6/15/15

Abstract

We show that for every 2-coloring of \mathbb{N} and every $k \in \mathbb{N}$, there are infinitely many monochromatic solutions of the system of k^2 equations $z_{ij} = x_i^{y_j}$, $1 \leq i, j \leq k$, where $x_1, \dots, x_k, y_1, \dots, y_k$ are distinct positive integers greater than 1. We give similar, but somewhat weaker, results for more than two colors.

– Dedicated to the memory of Paul Erdős.

1. Introduction

Using ultrafilters and results from [3, 4], Alessandro Sisto [5] showed that every 2-coloring of \mathbb{N} gives infinitely many monochromatic sets of the form $\{a, b, a^b\}$, where $a, b > 1, a \neq b$, and he raised the question of whether there is an elementary proof of this fact.

We use van der Waerden's Theorem on arithmetic progressions to give an elementary proof of a generalization of Sisto's result. We show that for any 2-coloring of \mathbb{N} and any $k \in \mathbb{N}$, there are infinitely many monochromatic sets of the form

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\},$$

where $a_1, \dots, a_k, e_1, \dots, e_k$ are distinct positive integers greater than 1.

We also show that for any 3-coloring of \mathbb{N} and any $k \in \mathbb{N}$, either there are monochromatic sets as just mentioned, or there are monochromatic sets of the form

$$\{c^{a_1}, c^{a_2}, \dots, c^{a_k}, c^{e_1}, c^{e_2}, \dots, c^{e_k}\} \cup \{c^{a_i^{e_j}} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\},$$

where c is a power of 3.

Analogous results hold for more than 3 colors. For example, for any 4-coloring of \mathbb{N} and any $k \in \mathbb{N}$, either there are monochromatic sets of one of the previous two types, or there are monochromatic sets of the form

$$\{b^{c^{a_1}}, b^{c^{a_2}}, \dots, b^{c^{a_k}}, b^{c^{e_1}}, b^{c^{e_2}}, \dots, b^{c^{e_k}}\} \cup \{(b^{c^{a_i^{e_j}}}) : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\},$$

where b, c are powers of 3.

In each case, $a_1, \dots, a_k, e_1, \dots, e_k$ are distinct positive integers greater than 1.

A somewhat different result was proved (using non-elementary methods) by Beiglböck et al [1, 2]: For every finite coloring of \mathbb{N} and $k \in \mathbb{N}$, there are $a, b, d \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\{b(a + id)^j : 0 \leq i, j \leq k\} \cup \{bd^j : 0 \leq j \leq k\} \cup \{a + id : 0 \leq i \leq k\}$ is monochromatic.

2. Two Colors

Definition 1. For $k \in \mathbb{N}$, an *exponential k -set* is a set of the form

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\},$$

where $a_1, \dots, a_k, e_1, \dots, e_k$ are distinct positive integers greater than 1.

Thus, an exponential k -set can be viewed as a non-trivial solution in \mathbb{N} , with distinct $x_1, \dots, x_k, y_1, \dots, y_k$, of the system of equations

$$z_{ij} = x_i^{y_j}, \quad 1 \leq i, j \leq k.$$

Theorem 1. *For every 2-coloring of \mathbb{N} and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists a monochromatic exponential k -set, that is, there exist distinct positive integers $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k$, all greater than 1, such that*

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

is monochromatic.

Proof. Let us first carry out the proof for $k = 1$, which illustrates, without the complications which will come later, the basic scheme of the proof.

Let f be a 2-coloring of \mathbb{N} , using the colors 0 and 1. We seek a monochromatic set $\{a_1, e_1, a_1^{e_1}\}$ where $a_1, e_1 > 1$, $a_1 \neq e_1$. We define

$$g(x) = f(2^{3^x}), x \geq 1.$$

By van der Waerden's Theorem on arithmetic progressions, there are $p, d' \in \mathbb{N}$ with g constant on $\{p, p + d', p + 2d', \dots, p + 16d'\}$.

In particular, with $d = 2d'$, g is constant on $\{p, p + d, p + 2d, \dots, p + 8d\}$, and $d \geq 2$. Thus,

$$\{2^{3^{p+jd}} : 0 \leq j \leq 8\}$$

is monochromatic with respect to f , say with colour 0, and $d \geq 2$. There are now two cases to consider.

Case 1. There exists $x, 1 \leq x \leq 8$, with $f(3^{xd}) = 0$. Set $a_1 = 2^{3^p}, e_1 = 3^{xd}$. Then $\{a_1, e_1, a_1^{e_1}\}$ is monochromatic, and $a_1 \neq e_1$.

Case 2. $f(3^{xd}) = 1, 1 \leq x \leq 8$. If there exists $x, 2 \leq x \leq 8$, with $f(x) = 1$, then $\{3^d, x, 3^{xd}\}$ is monochromatic and $3^d \neq x$, since $x \leq 8 < 3^d$. If no such x exists, then $f(x) = 0, 2 \leq x \leq 8$, and $\{2, 3, 8\}$ is monochromatic.

Now we turn to the general proof for $k > 1$. Let k be fixed, with $k > 1$.

Let f be a 2-coloring of \mathbb{N} , using the colors 0 and 1, and define

$$g(x) = f(2^{3^x}), \quad x \geq 1.$$

We require g to be constant on an arithmetic progression with $w + 1$ terms, where w is defined as follows.

Definition 2. The numbers $t_0, t_1, \dots, t_{2k-1}$ are defined inductively by setting

$$t_0 = 1, \quad t_{q+1} = (t_q + k)^{2(t_q+2k)}, \quad 0 \leq q \leq 2k - 2.$$

Then we set

$$w = 2t_{2k-1}.$$

By van der Waerden's Theorem there are $p, d' \in \mathbb{N}$ so that g is constant on $\{p, p + d', p + 2d', \dots, p + ewd'\}$, where e is large enough that $3^e \geq w$. Then in particular, with $d = ed'$, g is constant on $\{p, p + d, p + 2d, \dots, p + wd\}$, where $3^d \geq 3^e \geq w$. (The inequality $3^d \geq w$ will be used below only in "Subcase 2a.")

Hence,

$$\{2^{3^p}, 2^{3^{p+d}}, 2^{3^{p+2d}}, \dots, 2^{3^{p+wd}}\}$$

is monochromatic with respect to f , say with color 0, and $3^d \geq w$.

Let

$$T = \{j \in [1, w/2] : f(3^{jd}) = 0\}.$$

There are now two cases to consider.

Case 1. $|T| \geq k$. Let $x_1, \dots, x_k \in T$. Then $x_j \leq w/2, 1 \leq j \leq k$, and

$$f(3^{x_j d}) = 0, \quad 1 \leq j \leq k.$$

In this case, we take

$$a_i = 2^{3^{p+x_i d}}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq k,$$

$$e_j = 3^{x_j d}, \quad 1 \leq j \leq k.$$

Then

$$a_i^{e_j} = 2^{3^{p+(x_i+x_j)d}}, \quad \text{and } x_i + x_j \leq 2(w/2) = w,$$

hence

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

is monochromatic, with color 0, and clearly $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k$ are distinct and greater than 1.

Case 2. $|T| < k$. Thus,

$$f(3^{xd}) = 1, \quad x \in [1, w/2] - T, \quad \text{and} \quad |T| \leq k - 1.$$

Subcase 2a. There exist y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k , with the following two properties:

$$\{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k\} \cup \{y_i y_j : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\} \subset [1, w/2] - T$$

and

$$f(y_i) = 1, \quad 1 \leq i \leq k.$$

Then we have $f(3^{xd}) = 1$ whenever $x = y_i$ or $x = y_i y_j$, $1 \leq i, j \leq k$, and $f(y_i) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq k$. Hence f is constant, with color 1, on the set

$$\{3^{y_1 d}, 3^{y_2 d}, \dots, 3^{y_k d}, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k\} \cup \{(3^{y_i d})^{y_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}.$$

We may assume $y_1 < y_2 < \dots < y_k$, so that $3^{y_1 d} < 3^{y_2 d} < \dots < 3^{y_k d}$. To show that $3^{y_1 d}, 3^{y_2 d}, \dots, 3^{y_k d}, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k$ are distinct, we simply note that $y_k < w \leq 3^d \leq 3^{y_1 d}$, and hence

$$y_1 < y_2 < \dots < y_k < 3^{y_1 d} < 3^{y_2 d} < \dots < 3^{y_k d}.$$

Subcase 2b. There do not exist numbers y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k as in Subcase 2a. This means that for any

$$\{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k\} \cup \{y_i y_j : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\} \subset [1, w/2] - T$$

there is at least one $i, 1 \leq i \leq k$, such that $f(y_i) = 0$.

Now we make explicit use of the numbers t_0, \dots, t_{2k-1} defined above.

Definition 3. The sets $A_q \subset B_q, 1 \leq q \leq 2k - 1$, are defined inductively by setting

$$A_1 = [t_0 + 1, (t_0 + k)^{t_0+2k}], \quad B_1 = [t_0 + 1, (t_0 + k)^{2(t_0+2k)}] = [t_0 + 1, t_1],$$

$$A_{q+1} = [t_q + 1, (t_q + k)^{t_q+2k}], \quad B_{q+1} = [t_q + 1, (t_q + k)^{2(t_q+2k)}] = [t_q + 1, t_{q+1}].$$

Note that for each q , $0 \leq q \leq 2k - 2$, we can write

$$A_{q+1} = [t_q + 1, t_q + 2k] \cup [t_q + 2k + 1, (t_q + k)^{t_q+2k}],$$

so that if we take

$$[t_q + 1, t_q + 2k] = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k],$$

then A_{q+1} contains the exponential k -set

$$\{a_1, \dots, a_k, e_1, \dots, e_k\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}.$$

Also, recall that $\max B_{2k-1} = t_{2k-1} = w/2$, hence

$$B_1 \cup \dots \cup B_{2k-1} \subset [1, w/2].$$

We shall show that one of the sets A_i is monochromatic under f , with color 0.

We have $2k - 1$ pairwise disjoint subsets B_1, \dots, B_{2k-1} of $[1, w/2]$, and, since $|T| < k$, at most $k - 1$ of them can meet T . Hence, there are k sets B_{i_1}, \dots, B_{i_k} (we assume that $i_1 < \dots < i_k$) such that

$$B_{i_1} \cup \dots \cup B_{i_k} \subset [1, w/2] - T.$$

(In Lemma 2 below, we consider the corresponding union $A_{i_1} \cup \dots \cup A_{i_k}$.)

Lemma 1. *If $i \leq j$ and $y \in A_i, z \in A_j$, then $yz \in B_j$.*

Proof. From the definitions of A_j, B_j , we can simplify the notation to write $A_j = [a, b], B_j = [a, b^2]$. Then $y \in A_i, z \in A_j$ implies $2 \leq y \leq b$ and $a \leq z \leq b$, therefore $a \leq z < yz \leq b^2$, hence $yz \in B_j$. \square

Lemma 2. *Let $S = \{y \in A_{i_1} \cup \dots \cup A_{i_k} : f(y) = 1\}$, and assume that $B_{i_1} \cup \dots \cup B_{i_k} \subset [1, w/2] - T$. Then $|S| < k$.*

Proof. Suppose $|S| \geq k$. Let $y_1, \dots, y_k \in S \subset A_{i_1} \cup \dots \cup A_{i_k}$. Then by Lemma 2.1,

$$\{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k\} \cup \{y_i y_j : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\} \subset B_{i_1} \cup \dots \cup B_{i_k} \subset [1, w/2] - T.$$

But since we are in Subcase 2b, this immediately implies that $f(y_i) = 0$ for some i , a contradiction. \square

Thus, we now have $|S| < k$ and

$$\text{if } y \in A_{i_1} \cup \dots \cup A_{i_k} - S \text{ then } f(y) = 0.$$

Since S can meet at most $k - 1$ of the intervals A_{i_1}, \dots, A_{i_k} , there is some $q, 1 \leq q \leq k$, such that

$$f(y) = 0, \quad y \in A_{i_q}.$$

Since A_{i_q} contains an exponential k -set, this finishes the proof of Theorem 1. \square

Corollary 1. *Given $A, k \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists $M(A, k) \in \mathbb{N}$, $M(A, k) > A$, such that for every 2-coloring of $[A, M(A, k))$ there exists a monochromatic exponential k -set.*

Proof. The exponential $(A + k)$ -set

$$\{a_1, \dots, a_{A+k}, e_1, \dots, e_{A+k}\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq A + k\},$$

where we can assume that $a_1 < \dots < a_{A+k}$ and $e_1 < \dots < e_{A+k}$, contains the exponential k -set

$$\{a_{A+1}, \dots, a_{A+k}, e_{A+1}, \dots, e_{A+k}\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : A + 1 \leq i, j \leq A + k\},$$

which is contained in $[A, \infty)$.

Thus, given any 2-coloring f of $[A, \infty)$, extend f arbitrarily to a 2-coloring of \mathbb{N} . By Theorem 1, there exists a monochromatic exponential $(A + k)$ -set, which contains an exponential k -set in $[A, \infty)$. By compactness, the result follows. \square

Corollary 1 is the basis of the proofs for the results involving more than 2 colors.

Corollary 2. *For every 2-coloring of \mathbb{N} and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ there exist infinitely many monochromatic exponential k -sets.*

Proof. This follows immediately from Corollary 1. \square

3. Three and Four Colors

Theorem 2. *For every 3-coloring of \mathbb{N} and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ there exist distinct $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k$, all greater than 1, and $c = 3^d > 1$ such that*

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

or

$$\{c^{a_1}, c^{a_2}, \dots, c^{a_k}, c^{e_1}, c^{e_2}, \dots, c^{e_k}\} \cup \{c^{a_i^{e_j}} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

is monochromatic.

Proof. Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and let f be a 3-coloring of \mathbb{N} , using the colors 0, 1, 2. Using the notation of Corollary 1, define $W_q, 1 \leq q \leq k$ by setting

$$W_1 = M(1, k), W_{q+1} = M(W_q, k), 1 \leq q \leq k - 1.$$

We follow closely the first part of the proof of Theorem 1.

By van der Waerden's Theorem, there are $p, d \in \mathbb{N}$ so that

$$\{2^{3^p}, 2^{3^{p+d}}, 2^{3^{p+2d}}, \dots, 2^{3^{p+2W_k d}}\}$$

is monochromatic with respect to f , say with color 0.

Let

$$T = \{j \in [1, W_k) : f(3^{jd}) = 0\},$$

so that

$$f(3^{jd}) \in \{1, 2\}, \forall j \in [1, W_k) - T.$$

There are now two cases to consider.

Case 1. $|T| \geq k$. We proceed exactly as in Case 1 of the proof of Theorem 1, to obtain a monochromatic set of colour 0

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}.$$

Case 2. $|T| < k$. We make use of Corollary 1. Consider the intervals

$$[1, W_1), [W_1, W_2), \dots, [W_{k-1}, W_k).$$

The set T can meet at most $k - 1$ of these intervals, so for some q we have

$$[W_q, W_{q+1}) \subset [1, W_k) - T.$$

Thus $g(j) = f(3^{jd}), j \in [W_q, W_{q+1})$ is a 2-coloring of $[W_q, M(W_q, k))$ and by the definition of $M(W_q, k)$ there is an exponential k -set

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

which is monochromatic with respect to g .

Hence, with $c = 3^d$, we have $g(a_1) = f(c^{a_1}), g(a_2) = f(c^{a_2}), \dots$, so that

$$\{c^{a_1}, c^{a_2}, \dots, c^{a_k}, c^{e_1}, c^{e_2}, \dots, c^{e_k}\} \cup \{c^{a_i^{e_j}} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

is monochromatic with respect to f . □

Corollary 3. *Given $A, k \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists $M(A, k) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for every 3-coloring of $[A, M(A, k))$ there are distinct $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k$, all greater than 1, and $c = 3^d, d \in \mathbb{N}$, such that*

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

or

$$\{c^{a_1}, c^{a_2}, \dots, c^{a_k}, c^{e_1}, c^{e_2}, \dots, c^{e_k}\} \cup \{c^{a_i^{e_j}} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

is monochromatic.

Proof. The proof is exactly the same as the proof of Corollary 1. □

Theorem 3. For every 4-coloring of \mathbb{N} and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ there exist distinct $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k$, all greater than 1, $c = 3^d, b = 3^{d'}, d, d' \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k\} \cup \{a_i^{e_j} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

or

$$\{c^{a_1}, c^{a_2}, \dots, c^{a_k}, c^{e_1}, c^{e_2}, \dots, c^{e_k}\} \cup \{c^{a_i^{e_j}} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

or

$$\{b^{c^{a_1}}, b^{c^{a_2}}, \dots, b^{c^{a_k}}, b^{c^{e_1}}, b^{c^{e_2}}, \dots, b^{c^{e_k}}\} \cup \{(b^{c^{a_i^{e_j}}}) : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\}$$

is monochromatic.

Proof. The proof is virtually the same as the proof of Theorem 2, here using Corollary 3 instead of Corollary 1. □

4. The General Case

Theorem 4. Let $r, k \in \mathbb{N}$ and let an r -coloring of \mathbb{N} be given. If $r = 2$ there exist infinitely many monochromatic exponential k -sets. If $r > 2$, either there are infinitely many monochromatic exponential k -sets, or there exist $1 \leq s \leq r - 2$, and infinitely many monochromatic sets of the form

$$\{c_1^{c_2^{c_3^{a_1}}}, c_1^{c_2^{c_3^{a_2}}}, \dots, c_1^{c_2^{c_3^{a_k}}}, c_1^{c_2^{c_3^{e_1}}}, c_1^{c_2^{c_3^{e_2}}}, \dots, c_1^{c_2^{c_3^{e_k}}}\} \cup \{c_1^{c_2^{c_3^{a_i^{e_j}}}} : 1 \leq i, j \leq k\},$$

where $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, e_1, e_2, \dots, e_k$ are distinct positive integers greater than 1, and the $c_i, 1 \leq i \leq s$, are (not necessarily distinct) powers of 3.

In fact, given $A, r \in \mathbb{N}$, there is $M(A, k, r)$ such that, for every r -coloring of the interval $[A, M(A, k, r))$, there exists a monochromatic set of one of these types.

Proof. The proof is by induction on r , following the methods of the proofs of Theorem 2 and Corollary 1. □

We conclude this paper by proposing the following questions.

Questions. Does every r -coloring of \mathbb{N} give a monochromatic set $\{a, b, a^b\}$, with $a, b > 1, a \neq b$? Does every 2-coloring of \mathbb{N} give a monochromatic solution of

$$w = x^{y^z}?$$

Let $h(k)$ denote the smallest n such that for any 2-coloring of $[1, n]$ there exists a monochromatic exponential k -set. Let $W(k)$ denote the smallest n such that for

any 2-coloring of $[1, n]$ there exists a monochromatic k -term arithmetic progression. The proof of Theorem 2.1 shows that $h(1) \leq 2^{3^{W(16)}}$ and that $h(2)$ is bounded above, roughly speaking, by $2^{3^{W(s \cdot 3^s)}}$, where $s = 40 \cdot 3^{20 \cdot 3^{10}}$. Perhaps these bounds can be decreased a bit.

Acknowledgement. The author is indebted to the referee for many useful comments.

References

- [1] Mathias Beiglböck, *A variant of the Hales-Jewett theorem*, Bull. Lond. Math. Soc. **40** (2008), 210-216.
- [2] Mathias Beiglböck, Vitaly Bergelson, Neil Hindman, Dona Strauss, *Some new results in multiplicative and additive Ramsey theory*, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc. **360** (2008), 819-847.
- [3] V. Bergelson, *Combinatorial and Diophantine applications of ergodic theory*, Handbook of Dynamical Systems, Vol. 1B, Elsevier B. V., Amsterdam, 2006, pp. 745-869.
- [4] Neil Hindman, Dona Strauss. *Algebra in the Stone-Čech compactification. Theory and applications*, de Gruyter, Berlin, 1998.
- [5] A. Sisto. Exponential Triples. *Electron. J. Combin.* **18** (2011), #P147.